

Research Article

Hand hygiene: A Review on Malaysian Experience

Izmi Izdiharuddin Che Jamaludin Mahmud^{1*}, Nasuha Insyirah Mohd.Sollehim², Aina Batrisyia Abdul Rashid³, Nur Adriana Aqilah Md Noramrin⁴, and Farhah Syukriah Mohamad⁵

- 1 Faculty of Law, Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Pahang, Kampus Raub, 27600, Raub, Pahang; 0009-0009-2798-6387
 - 2 Faculty of Business And Management Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Pahang, Kampus Raub, 27600, Raub, Pahang;
 - 3 Faculty of Business And Management Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Pahang, Kampus Raub, 27600, Raub, Pahang;
 - 4 Faculty of Business And Management Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Pahang, Kampus Raub, 27600, Raub, Pahang;
 - 5 Faculty of Business And Management Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Pahang, Kampus Raub, 27600, Raub, Pahang;
- * Correspondence: izdiharuddin@uitm.edu.my; 013-3354389

Abstract: Hand hygiene is a multinational issue as it is often associated with infectious diseases and, in the worst case, death. Several international partnerships and organisations, like the World Health Organisation and Global Handwashing Partnership, have launched various awareness programs and guidelines to improve hand hygiene practices. In Malaysia, while there is a policy to increase hand hygiene awareness, studies show that there is still inadequacy in terms of laws and facilities to deal with this issue. Therefore, there is a need to improve the situation so that the cost of hand hygiene practice is more efficient than treatment.

Keywords: Hand hygiene, hand soap, alcohol-based hand products, infectious diseases, World Health Organisation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hand hygiene is hand-cleaning practices using soap and water or rubbing alcohol-based hand products. On the global level, two institutional organisations are leading hand hygiene awareness. First is the World Health Organisation (WHO), which champions research on the prevalence of transmitted illnesses among healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), which are attributed to poor hand hygiene practices.

The WHO introduces two mechanisms. First is promoting an annual festival called World Hand Hygiene Day, celebrated May 5, and its slogan is SAVE LIVES: Clean Your Hands. Secondly, an educational framework called WHO Guidelines on Hand Hygiene in Health Care. Inside the framework, WHO recommends five reminders to be taken for healthcare workers to clean their hands: (1) before touching a patient, (2) before clean/aseptic procedures, (3) after body fluid exposure/risk, (4) after touching a patient and (5) after touching patient surroundings (Nieradko-Iwanicka, 2020).

WHO provides visual examples of hand hygiene techniques for rubbing alcohol-based hand products or washing using soap and water with alcohol-based formulas. There are several steps for washing hands, which are in sequence: (1) wetting hands with water, (2) applying adequate soap, (3) rinsing hands with water, and (4) drying using a single-use towel. Meanwhile, there are several steps

for the use of alcohol-based hand products, which are (1) applying a palmful of the product in a cupped hand, covering all surfaces, (2) rubbing hands palm to palm, (3) right palm over left dorsum with interlaced fingers and vice versa, (4) palm to palm with fingers interlaced, (5) backs of fingers to opposing palms with fingers interlocked, (6) rotational rubbing of left thumb clasped in right hand and vice versa and (7) rotational rubbing backwards and forwards with clasped fingers of the right hand in left palm and vice versa (Nieradko-Iwanicka, 2020).

In addition, there is an international alliance called Global Handwashing Partnership. The alliance's main objective is to increase awareness of handwashing knowledge among the international community. They have an awareness campaign, Global Handwashing Day, every October 15 to remind people to practice hand hygiene by washing hands using soap and water.

2. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

Studies show that poor hand hygiene practice remains an alarming issue, as various gastrointestinal and respiratory infectious diseases can be attributed to poor compliance with hand hygiene practices (Aguzie et al., 2024). In impoverished nations, these infectious diseases are often associated with a high ratio of mortality among children (Khan et al. 2021). Therefore, hand hygiene is essential as a disease control and prevention measure, as there is an interlink between increasing awareness of hand hygiene practices and reducing infectious diseases (Jefferson et al., 2023). Furthermore, hand hygiene practices are more cost-efficient in dealing with multidrug-resistant organisms infections as compared to medical treatment (Wang et al., 2020).

3. FINDINGS

On the national level, the jurisdiction of promoting hand hygiene awareness is under federal and state Governments. It is because disease prevention is within the Concurrent List, allowing either government branch to formulate a suitable policy for hand hygiene. However, the federal government has a more significant role since medicine and health are on the Federal List, allowing it to mobilise resources and facilities greater than state governments. Therefore, the Ministry of Health presides over the task. The Ministry of Health published several guidelines, such as Policies and Procedures on Infection Prevention and Control (2018) to minimise HCAs, COVID-19: Management Guidelines For Workplaces, a preventive policy for COVID-19 (2020), a contagious disease that caused a series of national lockdowns for more than one year, and Malaysian Patient Safety Goals (2021) which provides strategies for hand hygiene compliance rate for hospital and clinic to be taken and the Guidelines for Control of Cosmetic Products in Malaysia (2022) prescribes the requirement for registration of cosmetic products which includes hand sanitisers and antibacterial hygiene wash products.

However, there are two issues to be identified. First is the vague law regarding hand hygiene products. It is noted that ambiguous or unclear laws could risk a policy failure (De Camargo, 2023). The first issue can be explained as the requirement for registering hand hygiene products, which under Malaysian law is generally construed as cosmetic or drug products that have medicinal purposes ("products"). The requirement to register products primarily derives from a piece of legislation known as the Sale Of Drugs Act 1952 (Revised 1989) ("Act"). It is considered an existing law, legislation that operated before Merdeka Day (31.8.1957), which allows it to continue until the present. Section 26 of the Act allows the Minister of Health to enact subsidiary / delegated legislation for procedural rules of products, which leads to the Control Of Drugs And Cosmetics Regulations 1984. Control Of Drugs And Cosmetics Regulations 1984 ("Regulation") requires two stages of registration: (1) registration of the product and (2) application for the license. Regulation 8 stipulates that registration must be done before the Drug Control Authority, and the consequence of non-registration is considered an offense under Regulations 7 and 30. The punishment for the said offense is prescribed under Section 12 of the Act.

However, it is noted that there is a possibility that the said Act is an obsolete statute that may lead to ultra vires, an illegal administrative decision. There are two issues: first, whether the Minister

can establish an authority, i.e., Drug Control Authority, to make decisions despite the Act being silent on that matter, and it is unclear in the language of the Act whether the Minister is the only entity that should decide while enacting the Regulation. Therefore, there is a possibility that the requirement for registration is illegal if the court construes that the Minister is the only authorised entity based on the interpretation of the Act and application of the doctrine of *delegatus non potest delegare*, which a decision maker cannot delegate its power to another entity unless the enabling statute expressly authorises it. Secondly, the offense for non-registration is restricted, which causes difficulties in law enforcement. It is because the Act itself failed to provide sufficient jurisdiction. It is illustrated in *Protherapix Sdn Bhd v PP & Ors* [2022] 1 LNS 2862, in which the court held that the offense of "possession" under Regulation 7 is illegal as the Act has never authorised it.

The second issue is the lack of awareness of maintaining hand hygiene among the Malaysian population. Various works of literature indicate one of the possible causes, and it is evident that Malaysian medical scholars such as Mohamed et al. (2020) and Tengku Jamaluddin et al. (2020) attribute the inadequacy to poor availability of hand hygiene facilities. Similarly, studies from foreign countries like Ataiyero et al. (2019), Midzi et al. (2024), Craig et al. (2024), and Suhita et al. (2024) concurrently affirm this issue. For instance, a study in Denmark illustrated that the increase in hand hygiene facilities like alcohol-based hand rub dispensers is associated with high compliance with hand hygiene practices among healthcare workers in elderly nursing home residents (Iversen et al., 2024).

DISCUSSION

4. CONCLUSION

There is a need to improve the policy concerning hand hygiene awareness and the available mechanism to achieve it by enacting new legislation so that the Ministry of Health can formulate a policy to change public behavior on hand hygiene. At the same time, there is a need to allocate the government budget for hand hygiene facilities as they are much more efficient than treatment caused by poor hand hygiene.

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